

Mining soil data of Switzerland: New maps for soil texture, soil organic carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus

Surya Gupta^{*}, Julia Kim Hasler, Christine Alewell

Department of Environmental Sciences, University of Basel, Basel 4056, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Maps of soil property are essential for soil monitoring, management, and conservation. These are available from regional to global scales, with global maps being urgently needed for global modeling and management endeavors (from soil degradation to climate change modeling and assessments). Currently, global maps are provided by SoilGrids (SG) and OpenLandMap (OLM). However, the number of samples used and spatial resolution for these maps indicate potentially a high uncertainty and leave room for discussion. A validation of global maps could be regional and national assessments with higher resolution data availability. Therefore, the objective of this study was to produce a new Swiss Soil Property Map (SSPM) for soil organic carbon, soil texture, total nitrogen, and phosphorus for Switzerland using higher resolution data compared to the previous global studies. To establish swiss scale maps, we fitted the Quantile Random Forest (QRF) machine-learning model for spatial predictions linking environmental covariates such as topography, climate, and vegetation with soil property data. Each model was evaluated using five-fold spatial cross-validation. The results showed concordance correlation coefficients (CCC) between 0.24 and 0.68 for predicted soil property. The new Swiss Soil Property Map (SSPM) as well as the global soil property maps were validated using the LUCAS dataset. The CCC for OC and clay maps of SSPM are 52%, and 24% higher, respectively, than the SG map. Therefore, this study demonstrates the potential impact of using sufficient data points to represent the individual country. Simultaneously we show that not just any additional data set will improve model performance. A well-planned high-resolution national soil monitoring is needed to improve the global maps in the future.

1. Introduction

Digital soil property maps at high spatial resolution are essential for soil monitoring, land management, and conservation. Furthermore, soil property maps are essential to model, predict, and assess the potential of soil fertility as well as soil protection, especially of soil erosion, retention of water, and climate mitigating carbon sequestration (Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016; Keesstra et al., 2016). As such, high-resolution soil maps are also crucial for the related derivatives, such as the modeling of climate change, food production, water filtration and flood prevention. Soil property maps of texture, soil organic carbon (SOC), nitrogen, and phosphorus are key parameters to assess ecosystem services and provide management guidelines.

Numerous studies have already produced national-scale soil property maps. Wadoux (2019) utilized the LUCAS dataset to create soil property maps with a 1 km resolution for France. Zizala et al. (2022) generated soil property maps for agricultural land in the Czech Republic. Liu et al.

(2020) developed soil texture maps for China using a national-scale dataset. Varón-Ramírez et al. (2022) crafted soil texture maps for Colombia, while Reddy et al. (2021) focused on India, producing soil property maps. Similarly, Malone and Searle (2021) undertook soil texture mapping for Australia.

Similarly, a few attempts have already been made to develop soil property maps of Switzerland. However, the available maps had some limitations. (i) The relatively coarse resolution due to a limited dataset. For example, SoilGrids (SG) 2.0 (Poggio et al., 2021) recently developed the global maps of soil property at 250 m resolution based on 14 samples only within the Swiss area. (ii) Soil property maps for the European continent excluded Switzerland as Switzerland is not part of the European Union, unofficially called the “Swiss white lake phenomenon” (de Brogniez et al., 2015). (iii) The legacy Swiss Soil Suitability Map (SSSM, soil capability map) from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (2000) is available at the scale of 1:200,000 (spatial resolution approximately 100 m, which is already an improvement to the existing global maps),

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: surya.gupta@unibas.ch (S. Gupta).

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but SSSM is developed mainly using agricultural soils (Baltensweiler et al., 2021).

In recent years, researchers from Switzerland made significant efforts to improve the mapping of Switzerland using spatially distributed datasets, more informative covariates, and state-of-the-art methods. Nussbaum et al. (2018) tested the linear and nonlinear regression models to map the soil property for the three Swiss forest regions of Berne, Greifensee and Zürich. Baltensweiler et al. (2021) developed national maps of soil property at 25 m resolution using various environmental covariates such as vegetation, climate, and topography. However, both latter maps target forested area only with no information on arable land and grassland.

A further hindrance is spatially imbalanced (spatially clustered) datasets as an input to machine learning models. Somarathna et al. (2017) demonstrated that increasing the number of sampling points in the training dataset could enhance the model's performance. However, Loiseau et al. (2021) argued that there exists a limit to improving the density of sample points, and beyond a certain threshold, the prediction accuracy shows little to no further improvement. Similarly, Figueroa et al. (2012) found that spatial clustering often leads to minimal or no increase in performance even with the addition of more datasets. Consequently, simply enlarging the dataset or incorporating additional datasets may not necessarily enhance the model's performance. To address the issue of clustering and imbalanced datasets, Richter and Khoshgftaar (2019) proposed using the learning curve method to determine the optimal reduction of imbalanced datasets for achieving spatially unbiased modeling. As demonstrated in their study, reducing the dataset to using a thousand points out of millions as input data resulted in the best model performance (Richter and Khoshgftaar, 2019). In addition to the question of spatial resolution and sample size of the underlying data sets, the sampling design and methods to acquire the measured data might be crucial.

Therefore, our objective was a soil property mapping of Switzerland

in 1) utilizing existing soil property data sets to augment the data points for the entirety of Switzerland compared to other studies, such as Soil-Grids (Poggio et al., 2021), EcoDataCube (Witjes et al., 2023), and OpenLandMap (OLM) (Hengl, 2018a, 2018b), 2) employing the learning curve method to determine the best and most consistent dataset for the model, 3) establishing links between OC, soil texture, nitrogen, and phosphorus and various environmental parameters (vegetation, topography, climate) acquired from remote sensing. We then applied the Quantile Random Forest (QRF) machine learning algorithm for spatial mapping, generating a high-resolution (30 m) Swiss Soil Property Map (SSPM) and uncertainty maps of Switzerland at four different depths (0, 30, 60, and 100 cm).

2. Study area

The mapping was conducted for the entire Switzerland, spanning an area of 41,285 km² (Federal Statistical Office, 2014). The country is divided into different topographical regions such as the Jura Mountains, Central Plateau, Central Alps, Western Alps, Southern Alps, and Eastern Alps, based on Behr et al. (2017), as shown in Fig. 1. The Alps cover roughly 58% of the country, the Central Plateau around 31%, and the Jura 11% (according to Swiss Federal Council data). According to the FSO – Swiss Land Use Statistics (2014) report, 23.4% of Switzerland is occupied by agricultural areas, 12.4% by alpine agricultural areas, 31.3% by forests and woods, 7.5% by settlements and urban areas, and unproductive areas such as lakes, rivers, scrub vegetation, wetlands, rocks, scree, glaciers, and perpetual snow occupy around 25.3% of Switzerland.

The average temperature in Switzerland from 1991 to 2020 is 5.8 °C. The highest annual precipitation levels, around 2000 mm, occur in the Alps, Alpine foothills, south side of the Alps, and western Jura peaks, while the northern plateau receives 1000 to 1500 mm of precipitation annually (Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss).

Fig. 1. The distribution of LULC classes of Switzerland. The CORINE LandCover (<https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>) of 2018 is used at 100 m resolution to show these classes. The map of LULC is further divided into the Jura mountains, Central Plateau, Central Alps, Eastern Alps, Western Alps, and the Southern Alps based on Behr et al. (2017) Fig. 1.

Soil formation in the Jura Mountains, certain Alpine regions, and the Pre-Alps is typically influenced by limestone or dolomite parent materials. The Central Plateau is primarily characterized by unconsolidated sediments, while the Western and Southern Alps are dominated by marbles, gneisses, schists, metapelites, and amphibolite (Zappone and Kissling, 2021). In terms of soil types, Switzerland is dominated by cambisols and podzols based on the Soil Grids World Reference Base soil map (Poggio et al., 2021).

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Training data

The training data for Switzerland was gathered by accessing various datasets, including the global data set WOSIS (Batjes et al., 2020), and European datasets like LUCAS (Orgiazzi et al., 2018) and SPADE (Kristensen et al., 2019), along with data from Swiss research institutes such as Nabodat (Rehbein et al., 2011) and Mayerhofer et al. (2021). The list of collected datasets can be found in Table 1. While analyzing the Nabodat dataset, we observed that certain samples had an organic carbon content surpassing 15%. As the limit value for mineral soil horizons is $\leq 15\%$ and to ensure the accuracy of the mapping for mineral soils, we excluded these samples. A summary of the statistics for the different datasets is provided in Table S1. The soil properties are assessed using distinct methods for each dataset, and details of these methods can be found in Table S2. Since the Nabodat has the data from last several decades different methods were applied over time (please see Table S2). We used whole Nabodat dataset for the modeling to cover all regions.

3.2. Screening the datasets for modeling

After consolidating the datasets, we employed the learning curve method (Loiseau et al., 2021) to determine the most suitable dataset for modeling. Including all available datasets as model input might not necessarily yield optimal performance (see discussion above). To assess this, we explored different combinations of datasets, namely Nabodat, Nabodat+Lucas, Nabodat+LUCAS+Mayerhofer, Nabodat+LUCAS+Mayerhofer+Spade, Nabodat+Mayerhofer, and Nabodat+Spade (please note that we did not attempt the Lucas+Mayerhofer combination due to its lower point density, and topsoil data availability only). For each combination, we fitted the QRF model and conducted spatial cross-validation (explained below). We then established a learning curve relating the model combination (x-axis) to the concordance correlation coefficient (y-axis) to determine the dataset that best suited the modeling requirements.

3.3. Soil and environmental covariates

The selection of covariates focused on factors driving soil formation, including vegetation, climate, topography, and parent material (Jenny, 1994). Vegetation was represented by the LANDSAT-based Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI; https://stac.ecodatacube.eu/lcv_n_dvi_landSAT_glad.ard/collection.json). For the modeling, we utilized

Table 1

List of soil properties available in each dataset, where n is the number of samples. The “**” indicates whether data is available or not.

Soil dataset	OC (n)	Clay (n)	Sand (n)	Phosphorus (n)	Nitrogen (n)
LUCAS	* (147)	* (149)	* (149)	* (150)	* (149)
Mayerhofer et al., 2021	* (208)	* (189)	* (189)	–	* (226)
Nabodat	* (9678)	* (67040)	* (67040)	–	* (3979)
SPADE	* (80)	* (150)	* (150)	–	–
WOSIS	–	* (14)	* (14)	–	–

four quarterly values per year (winter, spring, summer, and fall seasons) as median values for each year from 2005 to 2020 (a total of 48 layers) to account for the variations of Land Use Land Cover (LULC) across different seasons and years. For climate data, we used the CHELSA (Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface areas) temperature and precipitation dataset (Karger et al., 2017). The original spatial resolution of this dataset was 1 km. To downscale the climate data to 30 m resolution, we followed the approach used by Sanderman et al. (2018) and Hengl et al. (2017b), using bicubic resampling. Regarding topography, we used the swissALTI3D digital elevation model (<https://www.swisstopo.admin.ch/en/geodata/height/alti3d.html#links>). The original resolution of this dataset was 2 m, but we resampled it to 30 m. Additionally, we computed various topographic parameters, including slope, flow direction, flow accumulation, terrain ruggedness index, terrain wetness index, terrain roughness index, topographic positioning index, total curvature, profile curvature, and planform curvature using the swissALTI3D DEM. For incorporating parent material information, we considered a lithology map (Donnini et al., 2019), soil and sediment deposit thickness (Pelletier et al., 2016), latitude, and longitude. The complete list of covariates is presented in Table S3.

3.4. Quantile random forest ML framework

We utilized the Quantile Random Forest (QRF) machine learning algorithm to predict the soil parameters (Fig. 2). The choice of QRF for this study was based on the findings of Baltensweiler et al. (2021), who evaluated various machine learning models for soil property in Switzerland, with a primary focus on forest regions. Their evaluation revealed that QRF outperformed other models.

We overlaid the soil property data on the selected covariates to extract their values and constructed the regression matrix. This matrix consisted of dependent variables (to be mapped soil property) and independent variables (soil and environmental covariates). The dependent variables were linked to the independent variables using the QRF machine learning algorithm. Before running the algorithm, we fine-tuned the model by optimizing hyperparameters (mtry) for each soil parameter. After the optimization, we executed the model and obtained predictions for each soil parameter. We validated these predictions using both internal and external datasets, including an independent dataset. Along with the mean values of soil property, we also estimated the uncertainty associated with each soil property.

3.5. Five-fold spatial cross validation

The R space (Team et al., 2013) was utilized to fit the models and create the soil property maps of Switzerland. To fit the QRF model for each soil variable, we employed the R package ‘ranger’ (Wright and Ziegler, 2015). For the QRF model, the optimal value of the hyperparameter mtry (number of variables randomly sampled as candidates at each split) for each soil property was estimated through five-fold spatial cross-validation, while default values were used for other hyper-parameters (500 trees and a final node size of 5 points). To perform spatial cross-validation, we divided Switzerland into 1 km by 1 km grids and split them into five subsets, ensuring each subset contained 20% of the data. We fitted the QRF model five times, leaving out a different subset each time for validation. This process was repeated three times, and the average values of the predictions were used to compare with the measured values of the validating dataset to estimate accuracy metrics. The same procedure was used to determine the optimal mtry for each soil property. After finalizing the mtry values, we reran the model for each soil property using the optimal mtry and conducted spatial cross-validation again to calculate the final accuracy metrics. The relative importance was estimated of each variable using the residual sum of squares (RSS) metrics (Gupta et al., 2021). The variable with the highest decrease in RSS was considered the most

Fig. 2. The conceptual diagram shows the methodology followed to create the soil property spatial maps. The soil property and environmental covariates are linked using the Quantile Random Forest (QRF) machine learning method.

important covariate, with other covariates ranked based on their decrease in RSS. For uncertainty calculation, we utilized Quantile regression (QR) as a post-processing technique. This involved using model residues (differences between the observed and predicted data) to generate uncertainty estimates. The QR function allowed us to calculate any quantile (Rahmati et al., 2019). Detailed descriptions of the method can be found in Rahmati et al. (2019) and Kasraei et al. (2021). We derived the 90% prediction intervals (PI) by computing the quantiles at 0.05 and 0.95 using the qantreg option in the R package ‘ranger’ (Wright and Ziegler, 2015).

3.6. Criteria to assess predictive accuracy of soil property

The accuracy of the spatial cross-validation predictions was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), the coefficient of determination (R^2), and the Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC).

3.6.1. RMSE and R^2

RMSE is defined as.

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{SSE}}{N}}$$

where

$$\text{SSE} = \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2$$

is the sum of squared errors (SSE) between the predictions \hat{y}_i (predicted soil property) and the measurements y_i (measured soil property), and N is the total number of observations.

R^2 is defined as

$$R^2 = \left[1 - \frac{\text{SSE}}{\text{SST}} \right]$$

where

$$\text{SST} = \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2$$

is the total sum of squares (SST) and \bar{y} the arithmetic mean of the

measurements.

3.6.2. Concordance correlation coefficient (CCC)

The CCC (Lawrence and Lin, 1989) is a measure of the agreement between observed and predicted soil property and is given by

$$\text{CCC} = \frac{2 \cdot \rho \cdot s_{\hat{y}} \cdot s_y}{s_{\hat{y}}^2 + s_y^2 + \text{BIAS}^2}$$

$$\text{BIAS} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{(\hat{y}_i - y_i)}{n}$$

where ρ is the Pearson correlation coefficient between \hat{y}_i and y_i , and $s_{\hat{y}}$ and s_y are the respective standard deviations. CCC is equal to 1 for a perfect model with $\hat{y}_i = y_i$ in which case we have $\text{BIAS} = 0$, $\rho = 1$ and $s_{\hat{y}} = s_y$.

3.7. Validation of the soil property maps

The final validation of the maps was conducted using two independent datasets. Initially, we utilized the LUCAS dataset ($n = 150$) for all soil parameters, given its spatially well-distributed nature. However, LUCAS is limited to top soils. To supplement this, we collected 34 additional samples from various land use land cover types across Switzerland (called SwissAddition from here on, see Fig. S2). The sampling locations were determined using the Feature Space Coverage Sampling (FSCS) method, which proved to be more accurate compared to other sampling methods (Ma et al., 2020). To create the feature space for the FSCS method, we considered four key factors for soil formation: climate, topography, vegetation, and parent material. The R function ‘kmeanspp’ from the ‘Licor’ package was employed to perform the FSCS sampling technique. The collected samples were from areas below an elevation of 1600 m, as the sampling was conducted in January when many mountainous regions were still covered with snow. During the fieldwork, we used a geological drill or sampler to collect soil cores from the center of each site. The cores were divided into three depths: 0–5 cm, 5–20 cm, and 20–60 cm. However, not everywhere 60 cm was reached due to the presence of shallow soils in certain regions. Soil samples were brought to the laboratory for further analysis. In the laboratory, the soil cores were dried at 40 degrees Celsius for 48 h. After drying, the soil aggregates were crushed with a mortar and passed through a 2 mm

mesh. The total organic carbon content was determined using the Elemental Determinator CN628 (LECO), while soil texture analysis was conducted with the Mastersizer 2000, which utilizes laser diffraction to quantify particle sizes ranging from 2 mm to 0.001 mm.

To validate the new SSPM map, we compared it with the LUCAS and the SwissAddition datasets, as well as with the SG, EcoDataCube, and OLM maps. To ensure consistency, all maps were averaged at a depth of 0–30 cm, which corresponds to the surface soil data in the LUCAS dataset. However, the LUCAS data could not be used to validate the EcoDataCube maps since it was already employed in developing those maps. EcoDataCube is a recent initiative led by Witjes et al. (2023), with the goal of publishing environmental data for Europe at a 30-m spatial resolution. The EcoDataCube contained Landsat data from 2000 to 2020+, Sentinel-2 data from 2017 to 2021+, a 30-m resolution digital terrain model (DTM), and an extensive collection of soil property data, including >100 additional datasets. The authors created the soil property maps by associating these properties with a high-resolution remote sensing dataset and employing ensemble machine learning techniques. This approach enabled them to generate predictions for each property. They produced soil property maps for various time periods spanning from 2000 to 2023. For our comparative analysis, we utilized the most recent data set (2020–2023). For a more information, please refer to (Witjes et al., 2023) and EcoDataCube portal at <https://stac.ecodat.acube.eu/>.

The soil property analyzed for different depths from the SwissAddition dataset were also converted to a depth of 0–30 cm using the trapezoidal rule (Hengl et al., 2017a) for comparison with the SSPM and other maps. To extract the predicted soil property from the SSPM, SG, EcoDataCube, and OLM maps, we used the R package “terra” (Hijmans et al., 2022). The extracted values were then compared with the measured soil property, and the accuracy was estimated using the metrics mentioned earlier.

4. Results

4.1. Selection of the final dataset for modeling

After conducting rigorous selection using spatial cross-validation and the learning curve method the Nabodat dataset alone yielded similar results compared to all other combinations of datasets (including LUCAS, Mayerhofer et al. (2021), and Spade) for OC, clay, and sand content (Table 2 and Fig. S1). However, for nitrogen the combination of Nabodat and Mayerhofer et al. (2021) yielded a small increase in Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC) compared to all other datasets (Fig. S1). As a result of these findings, the Nabodat dataset was chosen for modeling OC, sand, and clay content, while the combination of Nabodat and Mayerhofer et al. (2021) was selected for modeling nitrogen. For a visual representation of the sample locations utilized for modeling, please refer to Fig. S3.

4.2. Importance of covariates and model performance

The spatial distribution of OC was primarily influenced by soil depth, followed by climate and topography (Fig. 3). Similarly, nitrogen showed high sensitivity to soil depth, while modelled phosphorus was found to be more related to slope and NDVI. Lastly, modelled clay and sand content exhibited a strong correlation with latitude, longitude (location covariates), and depth. The models' performance was further evaluated using five-fold spatial cross-validation for each variable. The accuracy metrics, including CCC and R^2 , indicated the highest precision for OC compared to the other soil parameters (Table 2).

4.3. Swiss soil property maps (SSPM) based on QRF

High OC levels are evident in the Jura mountains and the Central and Southern Alps, which are dominated by grassland and forest vegetation.

Table 2

Concordance correlation coefficient (CCC), coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE) of five-fold spatial cross-validation for all soil property. Nabo, L, M, and S represent Nabodat, LUCAS, Mayerhofer et al. (2021), and Spade, respectively. OC = organic carbon.

Dataset used	n	CCC	R^2	RMSE
OC				
Nabo	9678	0.688	0.525	1.643
Nabo+L	9825	0.689	0.528	1.645
Nabo+L + M	10,033	0.693	0.533	1.647
Nabo+L + M + S	10,113	0.686	0.526	1.66
Nabo+M	9886	0.692	0.533	1.640
Nabo+S	9758	0.685	0.519	1.659
Clay				
Nabo	67,040	0.553	0.393	7.94
Nabo+L	67,189	0.552	0.393	7.941
Nabo+L + M	67,378	0.555	0.395	7.926
Nabo+L + M + S	67,528	0.550	0.391	7.965
Nabo+M	67,229	0.551	0.391	7.955
Nabo+S	67,190	0.551	0.392	7.960
Sand				
Nabo	67,040	0.521	0.361	14.19
Nabo+L	67,189	0.517	0.356	14.25
Nabo+L + M	67,378	0.518	0.359	14.21
Nabo+L + M + S	67,528	0.514	0.354	14.27
Nabo+M	67,229	0.519	0.359	14.21
Nabo+S	67,190	0.516	0.354	14.27
Nitrogen				
Nabo	3979	0.637	0.392	0.254
Nabo+L	4128	0.639	0.420	0.25
Nabo+L + M	4354	0.651	0.460	0.236
Nabo+M	4205	0.642	0.443	0.244
Phosphorus				
L	150	0.241	0.101	24.059

Conversely, low OC values are observed in the Central Plateau, which is primarily characterized by arable land (Fig. 4a). For further information on the topological regions (Jura mountains, Central Plateau, Central Alps, Eastern Alps, Western Alps, and the Southern Alps), please refer to Fig. 1. Regarding sand content, higher values are noticeable in the Central, Eastern, and Southern Alps as compared to the Jura mountains and the Central Plateau (Fig. 5b). The uncertainty in the sand content map follows a similar pattern, with higher values being spatially associated with increasing uncertainties.

The nitrogen content map reveals low values in the Central Plateau and certain areas in the Central and Eastern Alps (Fig. 6b). Conversely, high values are evident in the Southern Alps and specific regions within the Central Alps. On the other hand, the phosphorus content map shows higher levels in the Central Plateau and Jura mountains compared to the other regions (Fig. 6a). These patterns are also reflected in the uncertainty maps for phosphorus and nitrogen (Fig. 6c and d), where higher values correspond to increased uncertainty.

4.4. Comparison to other available maps

Using the LUCAS data set for validation, accuracy metrics (Concordance Correlation Coefficient, Coefficient of Determination, and Root Mean Square Error) for OC, clay, and sand content of SSPM maps indicated better performance for the SSPM compared to SG and OLM (Table 3). In particular, CCC for OC and clay maps of SSPM are 52%, and 24% higher, respectively than the SG map. However, CCC of sand content of SSPM is low compared to the CCC of the SG. Note that the SSPM map for N was not compared with SG and OLM due to the unavailability of nitrogen content maps in these data sets. The SSPM also performed better than other maps expect for sand content map when using the SwissAddition dataset for validation. It illustrates high CCC for both OC and clay content than other maps, however, the R^2 is negative for clay content, which means that the model fitted for clay content predicted data extremely poorly compared to measured data. Additionally, when comparing the accuracy between LUCAS and SwissAddition data,

Fig. 3. Importance of the covariates for modeling soil property by a QRF model. The x-axis displays the average increase in node purity (the larger the value, the more important a covariate). The list of the 10 most important covariates is shown for each soil property a) OC, b) sand, c) clay, d) nitrogen and e) phosphorus. Soil depth belongs to soil covariates. The temperature of the coldest month (TCM), mean annual temperature, precipitation of the wettest month (PWM), temperature of the warmest month (TWM), mean annual precipitation, temperature seasonality (TS), precipitation of driest month (PDM) are climate covariates. Elevation, terrain ruggedness index (TRI), slope, profile curvature (prof_cu), and terrain roughness index (TROI) are terrain covariates. Latitude, longitude, lithology, and average soil and sedimentary deposit thickness (SST) are parent material covariates. Spring (SP), winter (W), summer (SU), and fall (F) seasons NDVI represent the vegetation covariates.

LUCAS performed much better than the SwissAddition data.

5. Discussion

5.1. Characteristics of soil property maps

The OC map indicates low values in the central plateau, which is dominated by agricultural fields. This is plausible as the intensive agricultural land use in the central plateau leads to relatively low OC due to soil disturbance caused by ploughing, a high number of rotation cycles, and export of crop residues (Reicosky, 2003; Smith et al., 2012). These results align with those of Stumpf et al. (2018), who also documented relatively lower OC in croplands compared to grasslands in

Switzerland using a combination of a remote sensing dataset and a machine learning model. In contrast, the maps predict high OC values in the Alps. This is connected to a relatively large input of vegetation and reduced decomposition of organic matter (Amanuel et al., 2018) during cold winter times and dry conditions on slopes in the summer. Furthermore, the mapped results of OC align with the observed Nabodat OC dataset (Fig. S4a).

The clay map indicates the highest content in the Jura mountains and the central plateau, with the lowest values in the Southern Alps (Ticino). The high amount of clay content in the Jura mountains is due to the presence of Opalinus Claystone, which is considered to be an over-consolidated clay with an apparent thickness of 160 m and an actual thickness of 90 m nowadays (Buocz, 2016). According to the regional

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of a) OC and b) the error map of OC for 0–30 cm soil depth of Switzerland.

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of a) clay and b) sand content whereas c) and d) are the error maps of clay and sand content, respectively for 0 cm soil depth of Switzerland.

databases of the cantons of Geneva and Vaud (part of the Central Plateau), the regions had clay content in the range of 15–30% (similar to our maps) for most of the soils. The clay minerals were inherited because of the post-glacial morainic origin of the materials and the low level of weathering (Dupla et al., 2021). Additionally, there is a noticeable reduction in clay content from the central plateau to the southern Alps, with an increase in sand content. Egli et al. (2006) tested the soil data of Morteratsch (Southern Alps) and revealed that the fine earth of the soils is very sandy (sand content 50–90%) and contains partially some silt (resulting from fluvial transport).

We predicted lower nitrogen content in croplands compared to grasslands and forests. These results correspond to the observed dataset (Fig. S4c). This might be surprising, as land management in Swiss

croplands involves continuous application of nitrogen in the form of organic fertilization with farmyard manure, and about 25% is applied as chemical or other organic fertilizers (FSO, 2018). However, the depletion of nitrogen due to harvest and leaching (Eurostat, 2019a, 2019b; Lee et al., 2020) clearly exceeds nitrogen inputs. On the contrary, forest regions showed high nitrogen contents, consistent with high OC contents, which has also been documented by Wibowo and Kasno (2021). In contrast to nitrogen, phosphorus contents are higher in the central plateau compared to other regions (Fig. 6a and Fig. S4d). The relatively high application of phosphorus fertilizer in arable regions, coupled with the strong sorption capacities of soils, leads to high soil phosphorus contents. The accumulation of phosphorus in arable soils has been a matter of intensive discussion in developed countries in the last decades

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution of a) phosphorus and b) nitrogen content whereas c) and d) are the error maps of phosphorus and nitrogen content for 0 cm soil depth of Switzerland.

(Cordell et al., 2009; Lemerrier et al., 2008). Tóth et al. (2014) observed higher soil phosphorus levels in regions with high crop yields and reported high fertilizer phosphorus inputs.

As expected, OC and nitrogen contents show dependence on soil depth (Figs. S5a and S5d). Higher OC is predicted in the surface or topsoil, due to either plant litter and root decomposition in the surface horizons (Kögel-Knabner, 2002; Poirier et al., 2018) or fertilization in arable soils. Yang et al. (2021) reported from the natural areas of China that nitrogen and OC are highest in the topsoil and decrease with depth. On the other hand, sand and clay contents do not exhibit significant depth trends.

5.2. Effect of number of samples

We observed that the best accuracy of the model was achieved with the Nabodat dataset using cross-validation. However, incorporating additional datasets such as LUCAS, Mayerhofer et al. (2021), and Spade (see Table 2) did not lead to any further increase in the model's accuracy (Table 2). This observation was reinforced when we checked the accuracy after adding the new data from the SwissAddition campaign, as it also did not improve the model's performance (see Table S4 in supplementary). Luan et al. (2020), confirmed these findings in their evaluation of the RF model's performance with different sample sizes (ranging from 10 to 80 sample sites) using cross-validation. They found that the RF model showed significant improvement when the sample size increased from 10 to 30 sites, but the improvement was less evident with larger datasets. Similarly, Moghaddam et al. (2020) also discovered that RF is less sensitive to the dataset compared to other machine learning models.

From these results, we could conclude that adding more data may not necessarily enhance the model's performance. However, it is worth noting that incorporating high-resolution environmental covariates

might improve the accuracy of predictive models (Hengl et al., 2021). For example, Žižala et al. (2022) demonstrated the importance of incorporating the bare soil mosaic in predicting organic carbon (OC). They observed an increase in accuracy after adding the bare soil mosaic to the model. Samuel-Rosa et al. (2015) observed that adding better resolution data would lead to improvements in model performance, particularly if the covariates are highly correlated with the dependent variables. In our study, we observed that climate data is sensitive to SOC, clay, and sand content (Fig. 2), suggesting that increasing the resolution of climate data could potentially improve the model accuracy. Furthermore, adding more covariates in our study also helped enhance the model's accuracy. For example, Moura-Bueno et al. (2021) included new covariates in their SOC prediction model, and the model with the highest number of covariates improved the prediction accuracy by 12% and reduced the prediction error (RMSE) by 22% compared to the model with the least covariates.

5.3. Comparison with other studies

The accuracy of the SSPM was assessed by comparing it with other maps using the independent LUCAS and SwissAddition datasets (Table 3). When we examine the results of our map in comparison to other national studies, certain similarities and differences emerge. For instance, Baltensweiler et al. (2021) used the Random Forest model to map soil property in Forest Land Use Land Cover (LULC) of Switzerland. They reported R^2 values ranging from 0.32 to 0.45 for clay, 0.30 to 0.37 for sand, and 0.185 to 0.215 for soil organic carbon (SOC) at various soil depths. These values closely approximate our results when assessed with an independent dataset, except for sand content values which is lower than the Baltensweiler et al. (2021) R^2 . In comparison with our five-fold cross-validation assessment, the R^2 values for OC and sand content are better than those of Baltensweiler et al. (2021). Similarly, Wadoux

Table 3

Concordance correlation coefficient (CCC), coefficient of determination (R^2), root mean square error (RMSE) of five-fold spatial cross-validation for all soil property. SSPM = Swiss Soil Property Map, SG = SoilGrids, OLM = OpenLandMap. Please note that regarding phosphorus there was no validation data available as we used the LUCAS for calibration. Additionally, the number of samples varies for different soil property due to the unavailability of values at certain locations. Only samples with complete information across all maps were utilized in our analysis.

Soil parameters	n	CCC	R^2	RMSE
		LUCAS		
		OC		
SSPM	141	0.46	0.29	2.02
SG	141	0.22	-0.51	2.94
OLM	141	0.013	-2.4	4.46
		Clay		
SSPM	143	0.54	0.29	6.09
SG	143	0.41	-0.21	7.93
OLM	143	0.26	0.08	6.9
		Sand		
SSPM	143	0.22	-1.95	21.6
SG	143	0.34	-0.50	15.46
OLM	143	0.15	-0.61	16.01
		Nitrogen		
SSPM	150	0.49	0.13	0.16
		SwissAddition		
		OC		
SSPM	27	0.24	0.16	2.59
SG	27	0.03	-0.92	3.93
OLM	27	0.12	-1.89	4.81
EcoDataCube	27	0.16	-0.019	2.85
		Clay		
SSPM	28	0.24	-5.01	11.47
SG	28	0.12	-10.42	14.71
OLM	28	0.014	-3.27	9.00
EcoDataCube	28	0.04	-8.20	13.20
		Sand		
SSPM	28	0.25	-1.89	22.08
SG	28	0.60	0.08	12.4
OLM	28	0.03	-0.78	17.35
EcoDataCube	28	-0.05	-0.33	15.01

(2019) utilized the LUCAS dataset to generate soil property maps at 1 km resolution for France. They employed convolutional neural networks and the Random Forest model and achieved CCC values of 0.57 for sand, 0.46 for clay, 0.23 for organic carbon (OC), and 0.31 for nitrogen content using the Random Forest model. Our SSPM model predicted better CCC values compared to Wadoux (2019) for both cross-validation and independent dataset assessments, except for the sand content assessment with the independent dataset. Likewise, in the study by Liu et al. (2020), a soil texture map for China was developed using the Random Forest model. They reported CCC values of 0.43 to 0.46 for clay and 0.45 to 0.50 for sand content across all depths using 10-fold cross-validation. The accuracy of our SSPM model in the five-fold cross-validation was found to be slightly higher than the results presented in their study. Notably, our study also observed better accuracy compared to soil grids maps, a pattern consistent with Liu et al. (2020) except for the sand content map. Similar findings were observed in Varón-Ramírez et al. (2022) study, where they compared soil texture maps to soil grids and found better accuracy. This difference could likely be attributed to the larger number of samples used in our study compared to soil grids for individual countries.

5.4. Effects of data clustering and sampling strategies

The original datasets, especially those related to sand and clay content as well as OC contained spatial clusters (imbalanced dataset) that could potentially impact the final maps of soil property (see Fig. S3). In our analysis (see Text S1), we did not observe a negative effect of clustering on the model's performance when we checked whether or not imbalanced data caused the model to overfit. The outcome might

depend on the methods used for the model and the way of tuning the model's parameters (Ying, 2019). Heung et al. (2014) also mentioned that, compared to decision tree methods, RF is less prone to overfitting. Gupta et al. (2021) tested the clustering effect on a global scale by implementing the random forest model with and without clustered data. The patterns did not change, except for a few sandy regions in Florida where high sand content influenced the results.

However, it is important to note that sampling strategies can also enhance the accuracy of soil property predictions (Adamchuk et al., 2011). Lagacherie et al. (2020), who have built 12,000 models using random forest algorithm for different spacings (from 200 m to 2000 m) and different spatial distributions (from clustered to regularly distributed), concluded that the performance of DSM models improved when sample spacing was increased. Furthermore, achieving a complete and evenly distributed sampling across the geographical space with a broad representation of the target soil property, led to enhanced DSM performance (Lagacherie et al., 2020). On the contrary, in our specific case, reducing the number of samples within specific clusters and utilizing a single sample for various grid sizes resulted in decreased model accuracy (refer to Text S1 and Fig. S7). Similarly, a recent study by Wadoux et al. (2019) demonstrated that not all sampling strategies could achieve this enhancement, indicating that the effectiveness of sampling strategies might be highly dependent on the specific circumstances.

5.5. Limitation of this study

While conducting this study, we encountered a few limitations. Firstly, data sets were limited for all soil parameters, as most of the datasets are available for the central plateau, while soil data from Southern, Western, and Eastern Alpine forest regions are scarce. Hence, having more distributed data from these regions could likely improve the accuracy of the results. Especially the data used for phosphorus in this study was very limited. Thus, there is a strong need for more spatially distributed phosphorus data to achieve better estimation. Moreover, all phosphorus data are from the topsoil (0–20 cm), so we were unable to predict values for different soil depths. Secondly, the soil data used in this study span from the 1980s to the 2010s, and we lack more recent data. While this may not significantly impact static soil properties, such as soil texture, it could affect dynamic soil properties like organic carbon (OC), phosphorus, and nitrogen. Thirdly, the Nabodat dataset used in this study is a compilation of data from several decades, with multiple methods employed to estimate OC and nitrogen (see Table S2). The variations in methods could introduce uncertainty into the modeling. We encourage readers to utilize uncertainty maps when using the soil properties maps. Lastly, regarding the modeling approach, only the RF model was used to generate the maps of soil properties. Exploring the incorporation of other models, such as XGBoost, deep neural networks, etc., in conjunction with RF, could enhance spatial predictions.

5.6. Use of the soil property maps

The new maps presented in this study can be utilized in hydrogeological studies that require information on spatially distributed soil property. These maps serve as a basis for modeling and assessments on a national scale and can inform decision-making processes for policy-makers, aiding in the formulation of plans and strategies. Furthermore, soil texture maps find applicability in many hydrological models, as soil hydraulic properties are determined based on soil texture information. The OC map can be used to assess soil health, as it is widely recognized as an indicator of soil health (Liptzin et al., 2022). However, it is essential to note that these maps provide mean values and are developed at a 30 m spatial resolution, making them less suitable for local or farm-scale management or point to point comparison to measure data. Additionally, we have provided uncertainty or error maps, which should be considered when interpreting the information presented in these

maps.

5.7. Exploring the path forward: ways to next steps

We observed an increase in accuracy for SSPM maps compared to other maps when comparing these maps with an independent dataset (Table 3). This increase was expected, as this study utilized a significantly larger and spatially distributed dataset than those used for developing other maps. However, the accuracy of the model did not increase after adding the additional datasets (Table 2). This leads us to conclude that data size is not always a limiting factor in developing better models until a certain threshold (Luan et al., 2020). Instead, we should focus on identifying the relevant covariates that can better explain soil property.

Furthermore, when validating the model, we noticed that its accuracy was higher when using the LUCAS dataset compared to the newly collected SwissAddition dataset. The primary distinction between these two datasets lies in their collection procedures. LUCAS collected five samples with larger volume across the field and across the first 20 cm depth mixing them to create one sample, whereas we only took one sample from the center of the field stratified into horizons to represent the regions. This difference in data collection procedures could be influencing the model's validation since it may not adequately capture the heterogeneity of the area. Given Switzerland's highly heterogeneous topography and climate, building a model that can cover all this diversity has proven challenging. Therefore, a more effective approach might follow two different paths: (i) Training the model for small and homogeneous regions. Several studies have achieved higher accuracy by adopting this approach. For example, Žizala et al. (2022) computed soil property maps for agricultural land in the Czech Republic at a 20 m resolution for depths of 0–30 and 30–60 cm. They obtained CCC values for OC and sand content, in both depth intervals, ranging from 0.53 for soil organic carbon to 0.79 for sand content. And (ii) gather a high resolution and regularly distributed data set of soil property for Switzerland like it is done in countries such as Germany is monitoring 8 × 8 km in the forests every 10 years, and 3200 arable sites (<https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/themen/boden-flaeche/boden-schuetzen/boden-beobachten-bewerten#bodenzustandserhebung-landwirtschaft>). Of course, the latter would have to be under the responsibility of cantonal and federal authorities and is beyond the capacity of academic research institutions.

6. Conclusions

We have generated a novel Swiss Soil Property Map (SSPM) for Switzerland, considering soil texture, organic carbon, and nitrogen at varying depths (0, 30, 60, and 100 cm). This map was created using a quantile random forest machine learning algorithm along with remote sensing covariates. Through a quantitative analysis based on CCC, R², and RMSE metrics in relation to the measured LUCAS data set, we have demonstrated that these SSPM maps exhibit higher accuracy when compared to existing global soil property maps like Soil Grids and Open Land Map. This indicates the potential benefits of enhancing the spatial coverage of soil property data beyond the currently available global datasets. The application of the random forest algorithm demonstrated its robustness in handling clustered datasets, and importantly, did not suffer from overfitting when using such data. Interestingly, our study also suggests that the number of data points is not always the primary limiting factor when developing superior models. Instead, the focus might be on identifying relevant covariates that can better explain soil property. Looking ahead, it is crucial to engage in future ground truthing and monitoring of measured soil property, given the limitations of (i) recent soil data for Switzerland post-2010, (ii) insufficient phosphorus data across multiple soil depths, (iii) inadequate spatial coverage of forest and grassland regions, and (iv) Coarse resolution environmental covariates such as climate and precipitation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Surya Gupta: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Julia Kim Hasler:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Christine Alewell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Surya Gupta reports was provided by University of Basel.

Data availability

The data can be accessed using this link: <https://zenodo.org/record/7821650#.ZDgSE3ZBxOQ> and code from this link: <https://github.com/ETHZ-repositories/Swiss-soil-mapping>

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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